

Strategy For HPC Integration (US) Whitepaper

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Introduction

High-Performance Computing (HPC) sites represent the most substantial computational resources available to the scientific community. Since the inauguration of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), these HPC facilities have experienced an astonishing 1000-fold increase in computing power, now reaching the exascale level. As upcoming High Energy Physics (HEP) experiments and other data-intensive scientific endeavors are projected to generate exabytes of data annually, there is an urgent need to efficiently collect, distribute, process, and analyze this vast amount of information.

HEP, with its extensive datasets and intricate connections to various scientific fields, has the potential to stand at the forefront of this integration effort. To fully harness the physics potential of this data and enable speculative exploration, it is imperative to explore and adopt new processing techniques, technologies, and resources. The convergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) with HPC further amplifies the potential for groundbreaking discoveries and drives innovation across these domains.

As we approach the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) era in 2029, the need to adapt algorithms and optimize code for evolving computational hardware has become more pressing. This period marks a significant shift in HPC, with the majority of computational resources now provided by accelerated processing architectures, such as GPUs, rather than traditional Intel x86 CPUs. While GPUs excel in specific applications with higher performance and energy efficiency, they require tailored workflow designs to fully utilize their capabilities. This transition demands a costly redesign of existing HEP workflows and the development of new AI-driven workflows that can leverage these advanced architectures.

There is an interest in the US funding agencies to make better use of the significant investment already made in HPC computing resources by HEP and related fields. This whitepaper outlines the strategic elements required for HPC integration into the HEP computing environments with a focus on the U.S. activities and interests, but most of the areas of interest should have a large overlap with other regions.

There is growing interest from U.S. funding agencies to maximize the existing investment in HPC resources across HEP and related scientific fields. This whitepaper outlines strategic steps to integrate HPC into HEP's computing environments, with an emphasis on U.S. activities but recognizing that many challenges and opportunities will be shared globally.

The role of GPUs in machine learning (ML) applications is particularly crucial, attracting substantial industry investments. The focus on AI/ML offers new opportunities for HEP but potentially reduces some existing capabilities. In the push for faster AI processors, industry has focused on lower precision calculations at the cost of improvements in the double precision calculations that HEP relies on for classical calculations. As this trend continues, HEP will need to investigate which workflows can be refactored to look like AI/ML and which may need specialized high precision optimized hardware. These challenges emphasize the need for data intensive science and the HPC community to partner at the design phase to ensure the appropriate resources are available to meet all the needs.

The intersection of HPC, data-intensive science, and AI presents both challenges and opportunities for the HEP community. Efficiently managing I/O and data access will be central to navigating this rapidly evolving landscape. Strategic decisions on code optimization, workflow adaptation, and future hardware designs will be pivotal in pushing the boundaries of discovery and innovation in the years to come. This document aims to describe the elements necessary to develop a comprehensive strategy for integrating HPC facilities focusing on US resources and identifying shared opportunities while acknowledging the unique challenges that lie ahead.

HPC Integration Strategy

To seamlessly integrate HPC resources into the HEP computing ecosystem of the WLCG, we need to address 5 key areas:

1. Provisioning

The traditional provisioning of computing resources in HEP relies on static allocations within a relatively stable environment, where resources are often available consistently throughout the year. However, HPC sites operate under a different model, typically characterized by dynamic usage patterns that fluctuate based on specific project needs and time-bound commitments. To integrate HPC resources effectively:

- **Adaptive Allocation Models:** Develop adaptive allocation models that can accommodate the variable availability of HPC resources. This might involve creating flexible scheduling systems that can dynamically allocate resources based on real-time availability and project priority, rather than relying solely on annual commitments.
- **Proposal-Based Access:** Establish a proposal-based access system tailored for HEP projects, allowing for periodic re-evaluation and reallocation of HPC resources based on ongoing needs and achievements. This ensures that the most critical HEP tasks receive

the necessary computational power when required. Explore the feasibility of longer term proposal-based allocations to ensure stability and predictability for the science programs.

- **Resource Scaling and Elasticity:** Implement resource scaling strategies that allow HEP workloads to elastically scale up or down based on the availability of HPC resources, optimizing the use of these high-demand systems throughout their operational cycles.

2. Interfaces

The integration of HPC resources with the WLCG requires a unified and streamlined approach to interfacing, minimizing the complexity and reducing the need for custom solutions:

- **Standardized Interface Protocols:** Develop and implement a limited number of standardized interface protocols that can be universally adopted across HPC sites within the WLCG. These protocols should be designed to handle the unique requirements of HEP workflows while maintaining compatibility with the diverse architectures present in HPC environments.
- **Interoperability and Compatibility:** Ensure that these interfaces support interoperability between traditional HEP computing resources and HPC systems. This includes compatibility with existing WLCG middleware and services, enabling a seamless transition of workloads between different types of computational resources.
- **Automated Integration Tools:** Create automated tools that facilitate the integration of new HPC sites into the WLCG. These tools should simplify the setup process, automatically configure necessary interfaces, and ensure that the HPC resources are immediately available for HEP workflows.
- **Cyber Security:** HPC systems have unique cybersecurity requirements due to their size and capabilities. The Interfaces need to be developed in ways that meet the strict authorization, authentication, and auditing requirements of HPC facilities.

3. Software

The evolution of HEP software is critical to fully leveraging the computational power of HPC systems. A multi-faceted approach is required to optimize software for these advanced architectures:

- **Software Design Enhancements:** Invest in the redesign of HEP software to be more modular and scalable, allowing it to efficiently utilize the parallel processing capabilities of HPC systems. This includes optimizing code for specific architectures, such as GPUs, and ensuring that software can take advantage of the high-throughput capabilities of modern HPC resources.
- **Portability Libraries:** Integrate portability libraries that allow HEP applications to run across different HPC platforms with minimal modification. These libraries should abstract the underlying hardware differences, enabling HEP software to be more flexible and adaptable to various HPC environments.

- **AI/ML Workflow Adoption:** Accelerate the adoption of AI/ML workflows within HEP that are inherently optimized for HPC environments. These workflows should be designed to exploit the strengths of accelerated processing units, such as GPUs, for tasks like simulation, data analysis, and model training.

4. Data

Efficient data management is crucial for the successful integration of HPC into the HEP computing ecosystem. The data workflows must be robust enough to handle the demands of HPC systems:

- **Scalable Data Ingestion and Export:** Develop data workflows that can ingest and export data at various scales and latencies, adapting to the specific needs of different HEP tasks. This includes ensuring that data can be transferred efficiently between traditional WLCG resources and HPC systems, with minimal bottlenecks.
- **Data Caching and Staging:** Implement advanced data caching and staging techniques to optimize data access within HPC environments. This involves strategically placing data closer to the computational resources that require it, thereby reducing latency and improving overall workflow efficiency.
- **Data Management Protocols:** Establish data management protocols that ensure data integrity and security when working across distributed HPC and WLCG resources. This includes robust error-checking, data replication, and backup strategies that protect against data loss or corruption during large-scale computations.

5. Workflows

Adapting HEP workflows to HPC environments is a complex task that requires careful prioritization and strategic planning:

- **Prioritizing AI/ML and Simulation Workflows:** Focus on optimizing AI/ML training workflows and specific simulation production steps that are well-suited to HPC architectures. These tasks typically involve high levels of parallelism and can benefit significantly from the accelerated processing capabilities of GPUs.
- **Code Reengineering for Reconstruction Workflows:** Identify portions of the reconstruction workflow that can be reengineered to leverage GPU capabilities. This may involve rewriting critical sections of code to take advantage of parallel processing or developing new algorithms that are better suited to HPC architectures.
- **Task Splitting for Partial Reconstructions:** Develop strategies for splitting HEP workflows into smaller, independent tasks that can be processed in parallel across multiple HPC nodes. This approach can help overcome the limitations of current HEP workflows that may not be fully compatible with HPC systems, allowing for more effective use of available resources.
- **Workflow Orchestration:** Implement sophisticated workflow orchestration systems that can manage the distribution and execution of tasks across both WLCG and HPC

environments. These systems should be capable of dynamically allocating resources, monitoring progress, and adjusting workflows in real-time to optimize performance.

By addressing these key integration elements, the HEP community can effectively harness the power of HPC resources, driving forward scientific discovery and innovation in the era of data-intensive research. The next sections of the document provide a more thorough treatment of the integration areas.

Provisioning

Resources at U.S. HPC sites are generally allocated as grants that must be consumed within a year. The amount of resources available for use at any given time depends on the overall usage of the HPC, with no specific constraints on when during the year these resources must be consumed. However, attempting to use a large portion of resources toward the end of the year can result in high resource contention. In contrast, LHC experiments, with their multi-decade physics programs and long-term computing requirements, favor multi-year allocations. Such allocations not only facilitate better planning of resources but also enable the experiments to secure resources that align with their long-term physics goals. Although LHC experiments invest in developing portable software that can be executed with minimal changes across various platforms, multi-year allocations would allow them to capitalize on additional investments needed for specific HPC centers. Conversely, shorter allocations are more effectively exploited at x86-based HPCs, where the required integration effort is minimal.

To address the variability in HPC resource availability and optimize their use, adaptive allocation models and resource scaling strategies should be employed. Adaptive allocation models would enable HEP experiments to dynamically adjust their resource consumption based on real-time HPC availability, preventing bottlenecks and ensuring efficient use of resources throughout the allocation period. Resource scaling and elasticity are crucial for allowing experiments to scale their workloads up or down in response to changes in HPC resource availability, maximizing the use of allocated resources without overwhelming the system. These strategies would also help in smoothing out resource usage, reducing the risk of contention at the end of the allocation period, and ensuring that critical tasks can be completed as planned.

Securing allocations at HPC sites is a labor-intensive process that differs significantly from the resource requests typically presented by LHC experiments to funding agencies. To make this process more efficient, it would be beneficial for experiments to invest time and effort during the initial phase of allocation requests, with a streamlined mechanism for subsequent years once the foundational principles are established. A good example of this approach is the NERSC ERCAP process, where initial allocations are handled by the DOE Office of HEP, and yearly renewals are straightforward.

Multi-year planning of experiment resource needs would be advantageous in leveraging HPC sites and their allocation models effectively. This approach would allow experiments to present comprehensive requests to HPC sites or their respective funding agencies, clearly outlining the resource requirements and justifying the need for multi-year allocations. These resource profiles do not need to be precise at the monthly level but should highlight the expected campaigns within a year and the corresponding resource demands. HPC sites are particularly well-suited for running large-scale campaigns over short periods, as they can allocate substantial resources for these limited durations. Such campaigns typically require pre-allocation of resources a few weeks before their launch, which aligns well with the preparation processes of LHC experiments. Currently, LHC collaborations operate with an open-ended planning process, where new work is prioritized as it enters the queue. However, to optimize the use of HPC resources, a shift towards a more capacity-based planning process may be necessary.

Different HPC systems are better suited to specific HEP workflows, and this is unlikely to change significantly. Therefore, the workflow management systems of experiments must evolve to orchestrate workflows on the most appropriate HPC machines. These systems must also account for the complexities of provisioning resources within specific HPC queues. Some HPCs prioritize large jobs that use a significant portion of the machine, which poses challenges for traditional workflow management systems. Additionally, the maximum allowed job length may vary depending on the job size; for example, a machine might allow a 24-hour runtime if more than 20% of the machine is used, but shorter durations for smaller jobs. To fully benefit from HPC resources, it may be necessary to split applications traditionally run together on grid resources. For example, the reconstruction application could be divided into components optimized for HPC execution and those better suited for CPU execution on the grid.

The issue of pledging HPC resources to LHC experiments requires further exploration. Currently, funding agencies, such as those in the U.S., provide funds to pledge resources according to the needs of LHC experiments within the WLCG framework. However, these agencies cannot guarantee sufficient funding every year, making pledged resources a flexible commitment rather than a guaranteed provision. Similarly, HPC allocations are contingent on the successful granting of resources, replacing the certainty of funding with allocation success. The feasibility of replacing traditional pledges with HPC allocations needs to be examined, along with addressing technical challenges like benchmarking and accounting for HPC resources within the WLCG context.

There are also notable differences between grid sites and HPC sites that must be considered for provisioning. Grid sites typically offer higher uptime and availability than HPC sites, which can experience downtime for days at a time. Additionally, grid sites support the virtual organization (VO) of an experiment, whereas HPC sites operate outside the WLCG's trust umbrella and require manual configuration to be usable by LHC collaborations. The issue of full VO access at HPC sites also needs further study, as these sites often have more restrictive access policies. Consequently, HPC sites should be reserved for well-defined use cases rather than treated as traditional grid sites.

Opportunities arise from the specialized architectures provided by HPC centers. Industry trends towards integrated accelerators on the same die as the CPU and unified memory could benefit HEP algorithms, which are often more data-bound than CPU-bound. Moreover, HPC centers are likely to offer superior network connectivity between individual nodes and connected accelerators compared to grid environments, which will be advantageous for large-scale machine learning applications. In the future, we anticipate the emergence of distinct AI HPCs, GPU-centric HPCs, and HPCs featuring unified memory and processor architectures.

Beyond the traditional use of scheduling applications on HPC queues and using on-host accelerators, there is potential in scheduling accelerator services on HPC resources. These services would handle processing requests from applications running on local or remote CPU resources, a use case that significantly differs from large processing jobs. This approach would require scheduling service instances and substantial external network bandwidth to transfer the necessary input data for computation. Investigating this use case could significantly increase the utilization of accelerator resources.

Interfaces

Currently, each High-Performance Computing (HPC) center operates with its own unique set of hardware, software, configurations, and policies. This diversity, while reflecting the specific needs and capabilities of each center, poses a significant challenge for researchers, particularly those in High Energy Physics (HEP), who need to access and utilize these resources effectively. To use HPC resources, researchers must often configure their workflows to accommodate these differences manually, a process that can be time-consuming, error-prone, and inefficient.

For HEP workflows—and indeed, workflows across all scientific domains—to operate smoothly, automation is crucial. Automated workflows reduce the need for human intervention, allowing researchers to focus on analysis and discovery rather than on the intricacies of configuring and maintaining computing resources. Additionally, automated workflows are better equipped to recover gracefully from faults or disruptions, ensuring that scientific computations can proceed with minimal downtime. Achieving this level of automation, however, requires significant information sharing and access from the HPC centers, often facilitated through well-designed APIs or other interfaces.

While some HPC centers, such as NERSC (National Energy Research Scientific Computing Center), CSCS (Swiss National Supercomputing Centre), and TACC (Texas Advanced Computing Center), have made considerable progress in this direction, it remains a challenge to run truly autonomous, fault-tolerant workflows across multiple HPC centers. This lack of standardization and interoperability between centers hinders the broader scientific community's ability to fully leverage these powerful resources.

In response to these challenges, the Department of Energy's (DOE) Office of Advanced Scientific Computing Research (ASCR) has introduced the Integrated Research Infrastructure (IRI) program. Launched in 2020, the IRI aims to streamline access to DOE's diverse set of user

facilities and resources, making it easier for scientists to utilize these capabilities. By 2022, the IRI had developed an Architectural Blueprint, identifying three primary “patterns” of scientific computing that span all domains supported by DOE:

1. **Time-Sensitive Patterns:** Computations that require rapid response times or need to be completed within strict deadlines.
2. **Data Integration-Intensive Patterns:** Workflows that involve the integration and processing of large, diverse datasets from multiple sources.
3. **Long-Term Campaigns:** Extensive, multi-year computational efforts that require sustained access to resources over extended periods.

The Architectural Blueprint also identified six critical “practice areas” that are necessary to enable these scientific computing patterns within the IRI framework:

1. **Resource Cooperation:** Ensuring that different HPC centers and resources can work together effectively, sharing workloads and data as needed.
2. **Cybersecurity and Federated Access:** Establishing secure and federated access controls that protect data while allowing authorized users to access resources seamlessly across different centers.
3. **User Experience:** Improving the usability of HPC systems to make them more accessible to a wider range of researchers.
4. **Workflows, Interfaces, and Automation:** Developing standardized workflows and interfaces that can be automated and easily integrated across different HPC environments.
5. **Scientific Data Lifecycle:** Managing data throughout its entire lifecycle, from acquisition and processing to long-term storage and archiving.
6. **Portable/Scalable Solutions:** Creating solutions that are both portable across different systems and scalable to handle varying levels of computational demand.

In late 2023, the IRI program was formalized within DOE ASCR, marking the beginning of initial work to define its management structure, governance model, and short-term activities. These early efforts include collaborations with pathfinder projects that will operate across ASCR facilities like NERSC, Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility (OLCF), and Argonne Leadership Computing Facility (ALCF). These pathfinders will help gather detailed requirements, test new technologies, and provide critical feedback on the IRI’s initial deployments. Additionally, technical subcommittees are being established to focus on the six practice areas identified in the Architectural Blueprint. These subcommittees will define the scope of work and agree on standards for accessing ASCR facilities.

It’s important to note that, as of now, there is no dedicated funding associated with the IRI program, although this is expected to change in future budget cycles. For the High Energy Physics (HEP) community, there will be an opportunity in late FY24/25 to contribute to the IRI’s work activities. To make the most of this opportunity, it is crucial for HEP to present a coherent and coordinated set of requirements rather than a collection of disparate, potentially conflicting requests. Some of the key needs for the HEP community might include:

- **Containers:** Ensuring that containerized applications can run consistently across different HPC environments.
- **Squids for CVMFS and Conditions Data Access:** Facilitating efficient access to data and software distribution services.
- **Data Movement via Globus and FTS:** Streamlining data transfer processes between different facilities and ensuring high-speed, reliable data movement.
- **Authentication for Long-Running Pipelines:** Establishing secure and robust authentication mechanisms that support long-term computational tasks.
- **Edge Services via Kubernetes:** Deploying and managing applications at the edge of the network using Kubernetes to increase flexibility and scalability.
- **Connections to Existing Workflow Systems:** Ensuring that existing HEP workflow systems can connect to and interact with HPC resources either through edge services or direct access.

Another significant opportunity for the HEP community will arise with the establishment of the High Performance Data Facility (HPDF), a new DOE user facility designed to support a distributed data facility with mid-range computing capabilities. The HPDF is expected to operate using a hub-and-spoke model, with the hub being awarded jointly to Jefferson Lab (JLab) and Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (LBL), and full operations anticipated by 2030. Although the HPDF is still in the early stages of design (having not yet reached Critical Decision-1, or CD-1), it is essential for the HEP community to prepare a coherent set of requirements to contribute to its development. This proactive approach will help ensure that the HPDF is designed in a way that meets the unique needs of HEP research, allowing the community to fully benefit from this new facility as it becomes operational.

By engaging early and presenting well-coordinated, detailed requirements, the HEP community can significantly influence the development of these cutting-edge facilities and ensure that their specific computational needs are met, fostering continued progress in scientific discovery.

Software Strategy

Software integration is one of the most challenging aspects of incorporating HPC resources into High Energy Physics (HEP) experiments. These experiments rely on extensive codebases to process vast amounts of data and generate detailed simulations. Typically, this scientific application software comprises millions of lines of code, developed over years or even decades by hundreds of contributors with varying levels of expertise. While software is critical to the scientific mission, maintaining and modernizing it presents significant challenges.

Historically, HEP computing resources have been dominated by x86-64 CPUs, with most existing software optimized for this architecture. However, HPC facilities are often early adopters of new technologies and increasingly rely on accelerators, such as GPUs, to enhance computational power while optimizing energy efficiency and cost. These accelerators are also integral to novel approaches and workflows, particularly those involving AI/ML techniques.

To effectively leverage HPC facilities, it is necessary to rethink how application software is developed and maintained. One of the primary challenges lies in the fundamental differences between programming for massively parallel accelerators and traditional x86-64 CPUs. Efficiently utilizing the available parallelism often requires deep knowledge of the specific hardware architecture, as well as the use of specialized languages and compilers to achieve optimal performance. In recent years, efforts have been made to develop portable parallelization strategies for heterogeneous architectures, which minimize the difficulties of running code across different hardware platforms. Additionally, updates to the C++ standard are increasingly facilitating the adoption of solutions that support parallelism and are universally portable.

In HEP, ongoing efforts are focused on re-engineering parts of the application code to run on new processing hardware, developing new code tailored to these architectures, and redesigning workflows to integrate AI/ML techniques optimized for accelerated processors. Significant progress has already been made in areas such as event generation, simulation, reconstruction, and analysis. Future experiments should consider these aspects from the outset of development. Although the effort required should not be underestimated, investing in parallelizable code will yield returns in terms of performance, flexibility, and maintainability.

Motivations for Re-engineering the Code:

1. **Performance Gains:** Accelerators can deliver orders-of-magnitude improvements in computational speed, particularly for tasks common in linear algebra and the parallel processing of objects in columnar analysis.
2. **Future-Proofing:** As computing architectures evolve, ensuring that code remains compatible with the latest hardware guarantees its longevity and relevance. The most significant industry developments are in accelerated processors driven by AI/ML applications.
3. **Resource Accessibility:** Portable code can tap into a broader range of HPC resources, unlocking greater computational capacity and flexibility.
4. **Workforce Development:** Proficiency in GPU programming and modern software practices is increasingly valuable, enhancing career prospects for developers and ensuring the sustainability of software development efforts.

Strategic Focus for Code Redesign:

The strategy for redesigning HEP code should prioritize identifying algorithms and workflows that would benefit most from accelerators and considering how AI/ML techniques can be integrated to enhance efficiency. It is essential to assess the cost-benefit of separating workflows that can be optimized for accelerators from those that remain best suited for general-purpose CPUs. In some cases, this may involve isolating components of a single workflow that can be accelerated. The development of portability libraries and unified programming models in recent years provides a pathway toward applications that are easier to maintain and can operate across multiple hardware architectures.

The Need for Vision and Leadership:

Transitioning to modern computational practices and hardware platforms mirrors past shifts, such as the adoption of C++. Successfully navigating this transition requires clear vision and strong leadership, with a focus on articulating the long-term benefits. These benefits extend beyond immediate performance gains to encompass a broader strategy for scientific advancement. Currently, limitations in software and computing resources are increasingly constraining the potential for scientific discovery and the ability to explore new ideas, but also hinder the ability to fully profit from software developments and leverage synergies with other disciplines."

Supporting Technical Evolution:

1. **Developer Training:** Invest in developing expertise in accelerator programming and portable software design within the team, with a focus on younger members who are poised to drive future developments. Encourage the acquisition of transferable skills that will appeal to a new generation of software developers.
2. **Programming Models and Portability Platforms:** Embrace tools such as Alpaka, Kokkos, SYCL, and modern language standards to create portable, maintainable code that can run across diverse architectures.
3. **Collaboration and Community Engagement:** Leverage forums like HEP-CCE (HEP Center for Computational Excellence) and the HSF (HEP Software Foundation) to share knowledge, resources, and best practices across the community.
4. **New Techniques and Ideas:** Harness advancements in data science, AI/ML, and other innovative areas to enable and enhance the pursuit of HEP's scientific goals.

Metrics for Success:

1. **Performance Improvement:** Demonstrable speedups in computation times for critical applications.
2. **Codebase Portability:** The ability to run software across a wide range of architectures with minimal modification, covering a broad spectrum of workflows.
3. **Developer Engagement:** Increased participation in training programs and active contributions to updating the codebase, reflecting a commitment to continuous improvement and modernization.

Storage and Data Flows

Effective data access is crucial for most HEP applications running on HPC sites. Whether retrieving data recorded by detectors during experiments or acquiring auxiliary information essential for simulating particle collisions, the efficiency of data handling directly impacts HEP's ability to fully utilize HPC resources. Optimizing data access, alongside efficient software and applications, is key to maximizing HPC site utilization.

Currently, permanent storage of large quantities of data on HPC sites is not anticipated. Instead, most available storage is used for transient data—data imported for processing or exported after being generated at the facility. To support these operations effectively, transient storage must scale proportionally with the compute capacity allocated to specific workloads. Additionally, storage performance must meet the demands of various workloads, particularly those involving AI applications. In this context, the network connectivity of the HPC facility is a critical factor; the ability to move data in and out of the facility at a rate that matches computing speed is essential. Beyond transient storage, HPC facilities should also provide storage for configuration files and access to CVMFS (CERN Virtual Machine File System), though the future widespread use of containers may eventually eliminate the need for CVMFS.

We can distinguish between two types of data interactions at HPC sites: data being accessed by applications running on HPC resources and data being produced within the HPC environment that must be transferred out.

Data Access within HPC Sites:

Large data flows within HPC sites involve accessing the experiment's data stored in large files, which are necessary for reconstructing particle collisions, simulating these events, or conducting AI training and inference tasks. By 2029, the volume of such data is projected to reach hundreds of petabytes, necessitating sufficient Wide Area Network (WAN) capacity at HPC centers, potentially in the range of multiple terabits per second (Tbps). To manage these massive data flows effectively, managed network connectivity (such as through the ESnet SENSE project) and sufficient buffer space at HPC centers will be essential to keep pace with processing resources. Ensuring that data flows efficiently through the internal high-speed network fabric at HPC centers is also critical.

Currently, there is not a common set of protocols and services for data transfer for the HPC sites, whereas the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) has standardized on WLCG-FTS and Rucio for data management across all experiments. This diversity in tools presents a challenge for HEP experiments, complicating the use of HPC sites. Moving forward, consolidating these tools would reduce the effort required to integrate HPC resources. One potential solution is deploying a managed buffer at the edge of an HPC site. However, this would require standardized buffer technologies or edge deployment capabilities like Kubernetes to ensure scalability and viability. This edge would need to connect to worker nodes via the HPC's high-performance network, allowing data to be ingested at rates of Tbps while also reading from worker nodes at sufficient speeds.

Security considerations are also crucial, particularly since current practices often require connections to be initiated from within the edge—a method that is atypical for WLCG and the HEP community. Finding solutions to facilitate this mode of access while integrating it with the global systems of WLCG will be important.

Small data flows, such as those needed to access software releases and databases, are also vital for initiating and executing HEP applications. WLCG uses CVMFS, cached through HTTP,

to provide distributed access to software releases, though container execution is becoming increasingly popular. Distributed database access is similarly provided via an HTTP wrapper using the same caching infrastructure. For each HPC site, providing an HTTP cache at the edge—either managed by the site itself or by the user community on edge Kubernetes installations—will be necessary.

Data Produced within HPC Sites:

Data produced within an HPC site must also be efficiently transferred out, and similar considerations apply as with data ingress. Large data flows leaving an HPC site are typically managed through WAN transfers, and the same need for consolidation of tools applies here. This process requires storing the produced data temporarily on site-accessible storage before transferring it out. Alternatively, data can be copied or streamed directly from worker nodes to an external storage provider, a method that requires robust outbound connectivity. Given the potential scale of these operations, particularly if large HPC resources are involved, the data transfer rates could reach Tbps. Small data flows generated within an HPC do not usually need to leave the site, but control data flows do require outbound connectivity. In all cases, lacking outbound connectivity necessitates specialized solutions, which should be avoided where possible. The DOE Integrated Research Infrastructure (IRI) initiative could play a role in consolidating and standardizing these processes across U.S. HPC sites.

I/O Patterns and Future Considerations:

The I/O patterns of HEP applications are also a critical consideration. Traditionally, individual HEP applications read input data and write output data sequentially on a single CPU core. As applications become multi-threaded, input data is still read sequentially, but output may be written at synchronization points or through non-blocking protocols that allow multiple threads to write to the same output file. Object stores offer a potential solution for asynchronous output at a much larger scale, enabling better parallel access and more efficient data handling. Edge services may be required to convert data from object stores to traditional file formats when data leaves an HPC site.

Auxiliary data flows, such as those needed for mixing additional particle collisions (e.g., PileUp libraries), often access data randomly, though these accesses can still be substantial in volume. Additionally, AI/ML training workflows interact with data differently, typically requiring repeated access to the same large datasets. This access pattern demands storage systems that are specifically tuned to handle high-volume, repetitive data access efficiently.

Currently, AI/ML training in the HEP community is treated similarly to end-user analysis, often as an individualized process with iterative and sometimes interactive access to a limited amount of resources. However, it is anticipated that in the future, production workflows will require large-scale AI/ML training, utilizing resources comparable to those needed for reconstructing particle collisions. This shift will necessitate significant advancements in storage systems and data management strategies to support these evolving workflows.

Workflows

High Energy Physics experiments require a diverse range of workflows to manage the complex tasks involved in data processing, reprocessing, Monte Carlo event generation, detector simulation, and AI/ML-driven analysis. These workflows are essential for interpreting experimental data, simulating particle interactions, and refining analysis techniques. Given the diversity of these tasks, workflows must be carefully tailored to match the computational resources available, including HPC environments. We have categorized the HEP workflows based on the IRI patterns, defined in the interfaces section.

1. Time-Sensitive Patterns

These workflows require rapid processing and immediate responsiveness, often necessitating real-time data access and quick turnaround times. Examples of time-sensitive HEP workflows include:

- **Detector Calibration:** Ensuring that detector systems are accurately calibrated in near real-time to maintain data quality.
- **Event Scouting:** Quickly analyzing subsets of data to identify interesting events that may require further, more detailed analysis.
- **ML Training and Tuning:** Rapidly iterating over AI/ML models, adjusting parameters to improve performance in real-time applications.

2. Data-Integration-Intensive Patterns

Workflows in this category involve the processing and integration of large, complex datasets from multiple sources. These workflows are crucial for the reduction, analysis, and interpretation of data, which are core activities in HEP:

- **Data Reduction:** Filtering and condensing large volumes of raw data into manageable datasets for detailed analysis.
- **Data Analysis:** Integrating and analyzing datasets to extract meaningful physics results, often involving complex statistical methods and cross-referencing with auxiliary data.

3. Long-Term Campaign Patterns

These workflows involve sustained, resource-intensive computations over extended periods, making them particularly well-suited to HPC environments where large allocations can be negotiated. Long-term campaigns often consume a significant portion of the total computational resources in HEP:

- **Event Generation:** Simulating particle collisions to produce synthetic datasets that mimic real experimental conditions.
- **Detector Simulation:** Modeling the behavior of particles as they pass through detectors, which can be performed with detailed (FullSim) or parameterized (FastSim) approaches.

- **Event Reconstruction:** Interpreting low-level detector signals to identify and characterize particles, a critical step in transforming raw data into scientifically useful information.
- **Data Derivation:** Reducing data further to create analysis-ready datasets, incorporating data cleaning, feature extraction, and other preprocessing steps.
- **End-to-End Processing:** Sequentially executing the full chain of workflows, from event generation to final data derivation or analysis, ensuring continuity and consistency across the entire process.

Matching Workflows to HPC Resources

Different HEP workflows have varying payload sizes and computational requirements, which affect their suitability for different HPC resources. For instance:

- **No-Input-Producing-Output Workflows:** These workflows, such as event generation, primarily focus on producing new data without needing significant input data, making them ideal for environments with ample processing power but limited data access.
- **Data-Input-Producing-Output Workflows:** Workflows like event reconstruction require both significant input data and computational resources to produce new outputs. These workflows depend heavily on the availability of high-performance storage and fast data access, making them suitable for HPC environments with robust data integration capabilities.
- **Data-Input-No-Output Workflows:** Analysis workflows, which often do not generate large new datasets but instead focus on interpreting existing data, require less computational power but may demand complex data integration and processing capabilities.

The availability and performance of storage, networking, and computational resources at HPC centers are key factors in determining which workflows are best suited for execution on these platforms. Additionally, workflow resilience is crucial; given the complexity of the tasks and the variety of components involved, failures can occur at multiple points. While general strategies for automatic recovery are in place and broadly beneficial, there is a need for more specialized approaches that address the specific challenges encountered at HPC sites.

The Role of HPC in Supporting HEP Workflows

While HPC centers can contribute to all three IRI-defined workflow patterns, their most significant impact may be in supporting long-term campaign patterns. These campaigns, which require extensive computational resources over extended periods, are particularly well-suited to HPC environments where large, negotiated resource allocations can be arranged. Long-term campaigns represent a substantial fraction of the total resources consumed in HEP and align well with the capabilities of current HPC centers, provided that sufficient data access and network connectivity are in place.

By effectively matching workflows to the appropriate HPC resources, HEP experiments can maximize the efficiency of their computational processes, improve the accuracy and speed of data analysis, and ultimately enhance the scientific outcomes of their research. Ensuring that workflows are resilient and capable of recovering from failures at HPC sites will further strengthen the integration of HEP with HPC, enabling more robust and reliable research outcomes.

Open Issues and Next Steps

This section identifies current open issues, evaluates whether they need to be resolved or tolerated, and provides actionable suggestions for each strategic integration area in the near term.

Provisioning

- **Open Issues:** Lack of long-term provisioned allocations on HPC.
- **Status:** Tolerable, with the current approach of using proposals and exploring dynamic and elastic scheduling.
- **Impact:** The absence of predictable allocations may render HPC facilities unreliable for the most critical workflows.
- **Next Steps:** Engage with funding agencies, WLCG, HPC organizations, and HPC resource providers to explore allocation models. Assess the feasibility of longer-term commitments and the steps required to treat HPC allocations as WLCG pledges.

Interfaces

- **Open Issues:** Lack of a common set of interfaces and protocols deployed at HPC sites.
- **Status:** Needs to be resolved.
- **Impact:** Without a common foundation, the ability to integrate additional HPC sites into a distributed computing environment will be severely limited.
- **Next Steps:** Collaborate with funding agencies, existing programs like IRI, WLCG, experiments, HPC organizations, and resource providers to document the performance, security, and technical requirements for interfaces. Form a community to develop a minimum set of common interfaces for HPC integration, focusing on standardization and reuse where possible.

Software Strategy

- **Open Issues:** Most HEP software has been developed for the x86 platform and does not benefit from accelerated linear algebra calculations available with GPUs.

- **Status:** Needs to be resolved, but can be mitigated through portability libraries and reliance on GPU-supported applications like AI/ML algorithms.
- **Impact:** HEP applications are currently limited to x86 CPU architectures, which are not advancing as rapidly as other hardware platforms.
- **Next Steps:** Conduct a survey among experiments to assess:
 - Readiness to use accelerated architectures like GPUs.
 - Needs and prospects for adopting portability libraries and unified programming models.
 - Expected evolution of software applications and the number of supported platforms by the time of HL-LHC.

Data and Storage

- **Open Issues:** HPC sites lack persistent on-site data storage, necessitating dynamic staging and export of all input and produced data. The data management systems must scale with the available HPC resources.
- **Status:** Tolerable, given that HEP data management systems are advanced. With the development of common interfaces for data transfer and access at HPC sites, the necessary scale should be achievable.
- **Impact:** Processing, simulating, and analyzing data require access to vast amounts of data. For HPC sites to contribute, data will need to be moved efficiently.
- **Next Steps:** Survey experiments on workflow requirements across three categories of access patterns. Focus on developing data challenges involving HPC sites to demonstrate the feasibility of completing workflows at the scale expected for HL-LHC.

Workflows

- **Open Issues:** HEP workflows have limited modularity for operational efficiency, and most are still modeled around an event loop. This makes it challenging to enable parts of event reconstruction on an HPC farm. In the near term, HPC facilities are unlikely to efficiently handle all steps of the processing chain.
- **Status:** Should be resolved, but progress can be made in the interim.
- **Impact:** HPC facilities will be most beneficial to HEP when they can handle a large fraction of workflows. While some workflows can currently run on HPC, further development is needed to expand this list.
- **Next Steps:** Work with experiments to develop a consensus on the number of workflows that could be run on HPC resources and assess the potential impact under the current provisioning, interfaces, software, and data/storage conditions. Identify the most limiting factors and study how resolving them would enhance the impact of HPC sites.

Looking Ahead

Looking ahead, the integration of High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources into the High Energy Physics (HEP) ecosystem has the potential to inject much needed computing resources as we enter the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) era and to serve as a catalyst to modernize the technology and the techniques used. With the advent of exascale computing and the increasing reliance on GPU-based architectures, HEP faces both a challenge and an unprecedented opportunity. The future of HEP computing will be shaped by our ability to adapt to these rapidly evolving technologies, ensuring that the vast computational power of modern HPC facilities is harnessed to its fullest potential for scientific discovery.

The five areas discussed in the white paper highlight the importance of embracing new computational paradigms, such as AI/ML-driven workflows and accelerated hardware architectures. As the boundaries between traditional HEP computing and HPC blur, it will be essential to develop modular, scalable software that can seamlessly operate across diverse and sophisticated hardware environments. The integration of standardized interfaces and advanced data management techniques will be critical in managing the vast data volumes expected in future experiments, positioning the HEP community to take full advantage of the technological advancements on the horizon, driving forward scientific progress and discovery.